

CONSTRUCTION OF COMPLEX Q-FUZZY SOFT INTERSECTION GROUP BY UPPER AND LOWER T-SUBGROUPS

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Abstract:

In this article, we construct a soft intersection group under certain conditions and a soft union group is investigated by this upper t-subgroups and lower t-subgroups with suitable examples.

Key Words: Soft Set, Soft Group, Soft Intersection Group, Soft Union Group, Upper T-Subgroup & Lower T-Subgroup.

Introduction:

Molodtsov pointed out several directions for the applications of soft sets. At present, works on the soft set theory are progressing rapidly. Maji et al. [15] described the application of soft set theory to a decision making problem. Maji et al. [15] also studied several operations on the theory of soft sets. The notion of soft set was introduced in 1999 by Molodtsov [14]. Since its inception, Maji et al. [15] and Ali et al. [2] introduced several operations of soft sets and Sezgin et al. [21] studied on soft set operations in more detail. And the theory of soft set has gone through remarkably rapid strides with a wide-ranging applications especially in decision making [6, 7, 16, 17, 23, 24, 19, 36, 25]. There have been also attempt to softificate various mathematical structures like groups [3], semirings [8], BCK/BCI-algebras [9, 10], p-ideals [11], BCH-algebras [12], rings [1], near-rings [20], mappings [18], soft lattices [13], substructures of rings, fields and modules [4]. Cagman et al. [5] introduced the concept of soft int-group which is based on the inclusion relation and the intersection of sets, and therefore more functional for developing the theory of soft groups. With the motivation of soft int-group, Sezgin et al. [22] moreover defined soft uni-group which is based on the inclusion relation and the union of sets and its basic properties of soft uni groups as regards normal soft uni-groups as well. In this article, we construct a soft intersection group under certain conditions and a soft union group is investigated by this upper t-subgroups and lower t-subgroups with suitable examples.

Preliminaries and Basic Concepts:

Definition 2.1: A pair (F, A) is called a soft set over U , where F is a mapping given by $F: A \rightarrow P(U)$. In other words, a soft set over U is a parameterized family of subsets of the universe U . Note that a soft set (F, A) can be denoted by F_A . In this case, when we define more than one soft set in some subsets A, B, C of parameters E , the soft sets will be denoted by F_A, F_B, F_C , respectively. On the other case, when we define more than one soft set in a subset A of the set of parameters E , the soft sets will be denoted by F_A, G_A, H_A , respectively.

Definition 2.2: The relative complement of the soft set F_A over U is denoted by F_A^c , where $F_A^c: A \rightarrow P(U)$ is a mapping given as $F_A^c(a) = U \setminus F_A(a)$, for all $a \in A$.

Definition 2.3: Let F_A and G_B be two soft sets over U such that $A \cap B \neq \Phi$. The restricted intersection of F_A and G_B is denoted by $F_A \cap G_B$ and is defined as $F_A \cap G_B = (H, C)$, where $C = A \cap B$ and for all $c \in C$, $H(c) = F(c) \cap G(c)$.

Definition 2.4: Let F_A and G_B be two soft sets over U such that $A \cap B \neq \Phi$. The restricted union of F_A and G_B is denoted by $F_A \cup G_B$ and is defined as $F_A \cup G_B = (H, C)$, where $C = A \cap B$ and for all $c \in C$, $H(c) = F(c) \cup G(c)$.

Definition 2.5: Let F_A and G_B be soft sets over the common universe U and ψ be a function from A to B . Then we can define the soft set $\psi(F_A)$ over U , where $\psi(F_A): B \rightarrow P(U)$ is a set valued function defined by $\psi(F_A)(b) = \bigcup \{F(a) \mid a \in A \text{ and } \psi(a) = b\}$,

If $\psi^{-1}(b) \neq \Phi$, $= 0$ otherwise for all $b \in B$. Here, $\psi(F_A)$ is called the soft image of F_A under ψ . Moreover we can define a soft set $\psi^{-1}(G_B)$ over U , where $\psi^{-1}(G_B): A \rightarrow P(U)$ is a set-valued function defined by $\psi^{-1}(G_B)(a) = G(\psi(a))$ for all $a \in A$. Then, $\psi^{-1}(G_B)$ is called the soft pre image (or inverse image) of G_B under ψ .

Definition 2.6: Let F_A and G_B be soft sets over the common universe U and ψ be a function from A to B . Then we can define the soft set $\psi^*(F_A)$ over U , where $\psi^*(F_A): B \rightarrow P(U)$ is a set-valued function defined by $\psi^*(F_A)(b) = \bigcap \{F(a) \mid a \in A \text{ and } \psi(a) = b\}$, if $\psi^{-1}(b) \neq \Phi$, $= 0$ otherwise for all $b \in B$. Here, $\psi^*(F_A)$ is called the soft anti image of F_A under ψ .

Definition 2.7: Let f_A be a soft set over U and α be a subset of U . Then, upper α -inclusion of a soft set f_A , denoted by f_A^α , is defined as $f_A^\alpha = \{x \in A : f_A(x) \supseteq \alpha\}$

Definition 2.8: Let X be any non-empty set. A mapping $\delta: X \rightarrow [0,1]$ is called fuzzy set on X .

Definition 2.9: A complex fuzzy soft subset A, defined on a universe of discourse X, is characterized by a membership function $\tau_A(x)$ that assigns any element $x \in X$ and a complex valued grade of membership in A. The values of $\tau_A(x)$ all lie within the unit circle in the complex plane and are thus all of the form $P_A(x) e^{j\mu_A(x)}$ where $P_A(x)$ and $e^{j\mu_A(x)}$ are both real valued and $P_A(x) \in [0,1]$. Here $P_A(x)$ is termed as amplitude term and $e^{j\mu_A(x)}$ is termed as phase term.

The complex fuzzy soft set may be represented in the set form as $A = \{(x, \tau_A(x)) / x \in X\}$. It is denoted by CFSS. The phase term of complex membership function belongs to $(0, 2\pi)$. Now we take those forms which presented to define the game of winner, neutral and loser.

$$\mu_{A \cup B}(x) = \begin{cases} \mu_A(x) & \text{if } p_A > p_B \\ \mu_B(x) & \text{if } p_A < p_B \end{cases}$$

This is a novel concept and it is the generalization of the concept “winner take all” for the union of phase terms.

Definition 2.10: Let $X = \{x_1, x_2, x_3\}$ be a universe of discourse. Let A and B be complex fuzzy soft sets in X as shown below.

$$\begin{aligned} A &= \{0.6 e^{i(0.8)}, 0.3 e^{i\frac{3\pi}{4}}, 0.5 e^{i(0.3)}\} \\ B &= \{0.8 e^{i(0.9)}, 0.1 e^{i\frac{\pi}{4}}, 0.4 e^{i(0.5)}\} \\ A \cup B &= \{0.8 e^{i(0.9)}, 0.3 e^{i\frac{3\pi}{4}}, 0.5 e^{i(0.3)}\} \end{aligned}$$

We can easily calculate the phase terms $e^{i\mu_{A \cap B}(x)}$ on the same line by winner, neutral and loser game.

Definition 2.11: Here a complex fuzzy soft subset A of a group G is said to be a complex fuzzy soft subgroup of G if for all $x, y \in G$

$$(CFSSG1) \quad A(xy) \geq \min \{A(x), A(y)\},$$

(CFSSG2) $A(x^{-1}) \geq A(x)$ where the product x and y is denoted by xy and the inverse of x by x^{-1} . It is well known and easy to see that a complex fuzzy soft subgroup G satisfies $A(x) \leq A(e)$ and $A(x^{-1}) = A(x)$ for all $x \in G$, where ‘e’ is the identity of G.

Some Applications of Complex Soft Intersection Structures:

Theorem 3.1: Let δ_G be a complex Q-fuzzy soft set over U, $\delta_G \supseteq^t$ be upper t-subgroups of δ_G for each $t \subseteq U$ and the set $\text{Im}(\delta_G)$ be ordered by combination. Then, δ_G is a complex fuzzy soft intersection group over U.

Proof: Let $x, y \in G$ and $q \in Q$ and $\delta_G(x, q) = t_1$ and $\delta_G(y, q) = t_2$.

Suppose that $t_1 \subseteq t_2$. It is obvious that $x \in \delta_G \supseteq^t 1$ and $y \in \delta_G \supseteq^t 2$.

Since $t_1 \subseteq t_2$, It is follows that $x, y \in \delta_G \supseteq^t 1$ and since $\delta_G \supseteq^t$ is a subgroup of G for all $t \subseteq U$, it follows that $x y^{-1} \in \delta_G \supseteq^t 1$. Hence $\delta_G(x y^{-1}, q) \geq t_1 = t_1 \cap t_2 = \min \{ \delta_G(x, q), \delta_G(y, q) \}$. Thus δ_G is a complex Q-fuzzy soft intersection group over U.

Theorem 3.2: Let δ_G be a Complex Q-fuzzy soft set over U. $\delta_G \subseteq^t$ be lower t-subgroups of δ_G for each $t \subseteq U$ and the set $\text{Im}(\delta_G)$ by ordered by combination. Then δ_G is a complex Q – fuzzy soft Union group over U.

Proof: Let $x, y \in G$, $q \in Q$ and $\delta_G(x, q) = t_1$ and $\delta_G(y, q) = t_2$

Suppose that $t_1 \subseteq t_2$. It is obvious that $x \in \delta_G \subseteq^t 2$ and since $\delta_G \subseteq^t$ is a subgroup of G for all $t \subseteq U$, it follows

$$\text{that } xy^{-1} \in \delta_G \subseteq^t 2$$

$$\text{Hence } \delta_G(xy^{-1}, q) \leq t_2 \leq t_1 \cup t_2 = \max \{ \delta_G(x, q), \delta_G(y, q) \}$$

Therefore, δ_G is a CQFSU – Group over U. From now on, it will be more connected with a CQFSI – group and its upper t – subgroups.

Note 3.4: If δ_G is a CQFSI – group over U, then the set $\text{Im}(\delta_G)$ does not need to be ordered by combination as in the case of the following example.

Example 3.5: Assume that $U = S_3$ is the universal set and $G = Z_6$ is the set of parameters.

If a CQFSS is constructed by $\delta_G(0, q) = S_3$;

$$\begin{aligned} \delta_G(1, q) &= \delta_G(5, q) = \{(12), (13), (132)\} \\ \delta_G(2, q) &= \delta_G(4, q) = \{(12), (13), (23), (123), (132)\} \\ \delta_G(3, q) &= \{(1), (12), (13), (132)\} \end{aligned}$$

then δ_G is a CQFSI – group over U, whose image set is not ordered by combination.

$$\text{Note that } \delta_G \supseteq^{S_3} = \{0\}$$

$$\delta_G \supseteq^{\{(1), (12), (13), (132)\}} = \{0, 3\}$$

$$\delta_G \supseteq^{\{(12), (13), (23), (123), (132)\}} = \{0, 2, 4\}$$

$$\delta_G \supseteq^{\{(1), (12), (13), (132)\}} = Z_6$$

Thus upper t – subgroup $\{0\}$ attains an infimum on 0, $\{0, 3\}$ on 3, $\{0, 2, 4\}$ on 2 and 4, since $\delta_G(2, q) = \delta_G(4, q)$ and Z_6 on 1 and 5.

Theorem 3.6: Any subgroup H of a group G can be realized as an upper t – subgroup of some CQFSI – group over U.

Proof: Let δ_G be a CQFS – set over U defined by

$$\delta_G(x, q) = t, \text{ if } x \in H \\ = \Phi, \text{ if } x \notin H \text{ then } \delta_G \text{ is a CQFSI – group over U.}$$

Let $a, b \in G$.

Case (i) : Suppose $a \in H$ and $b \in H$, then $ab \in H$.

It follows that $\delta_G(ab, q) = t$ and $\delta_G(a, q) = \delta_G(b, q) = t$.

Thus, $\delta_G(ab, q) \geq \min \{ \delta_G(a, q), \delta_G(b, q) \}$.

And also if $a \in H$, then so is a^{-1} , thus $\delta_G(a, q) = \delta_G(a^{-1}, q) = t$.

Case (ii) : Now, suppose $a \in H$ and $b \notin H$ then $ab \notin H$. It follows that

$$\delta_G(a, q) = t \text{ and } \delta_G(b, q) = \delta_G(ab, q) = \Phi.$$

Therefore, $\delta_G(ab, q) \geq \min \{ \delta_G(a, q), \delta_G(b, q) \}$,

Furthermore $\delta_G(a, q) = \delta_G(a^{-1}, q)$ if $a \in H$ or $a \notin H$.

Case (iii) : Now, suppose that $a \notin H$ and $b \notin H$. Then either $a, b \in H$ or $a, b \notin H$. It is easy to show that in any cases, $\delta_G(ab, q) \geq \min \{ \delta_G(a, q), \delta_G(b, q) \}$,

$$\text{And } \delta_G(a, q) = \delta_G(a^{-1}, q).$$

Hence δ_G is a CQFSI – group over U. Therefore, for this CQFSI group, $\delta_G^{\exists t} = H$.

Note 3.7: It is known that if δ_G is a CQFSI group over U, then $\delta_G(e, q) \geq \delta_G(x, q)$ for all $x \in G$ and $q \in Q$.

Let $\delta_G(e, q) \geq t_e$, then it turns out to be an interesting case to investigate the upper t_e subgroup of $\delta_G^{\exists t} e$ of G. Because if $x \in \delta_G^{\exists t} e$, then $\delta_G(x, q) \geq t = \delta_G(e, q)$ and it appears that only $e \in \delta_G^{\exists t} e$. But that is not always the case as seen in the following example.

Example 3.8: Consider the CQFSI – group in theorem 3.6. Assume that $H \neq \{ e \}$ and $H \neq G$. It is known that δ_G is a CQFSI – group over U and $\text{Im}(\delta_G) = \{ \Phi, t \}$. Thus, two upper t – subgroups are $\delta_G^{\exists \Phi} = G$ and $\delta_G^{\exists t} = \{ x \in G / \delta_G(x, q) \geq t \} = H$. Since $e \in H$, $\delta_G(e, q) = t$; but $\delta_G^{\exists t} = H$, which is not equal to “e”.

Definition 3.9: Let δ_G be a CQFSU – group over U. Then e – set of δ_G , denoted by G_{δ_G} , is defined as $G_{\delta_G} = \{ x \in G / \delta_G(x, q) = \delta_G(e, q) \}$

Theorem 3.10: Let δ_G be a CQFSI – group over U. If $\delta_G(e, q) = t_e$, then $\delta_G^{\exists t_e} = G_{\delta_G}$.

$$\text{Proof: } \delta_G^{\exists t_e} = \{ x \in G / \delta_G(x, q) \geq t_e \} \\ = \{ x \in G / \delta_G(x, q) = t_e \}$$

Since $t_e \geq \delta_G(x, q)$ for all $x \in G$ and $q \in Q$. $\delta_G^{\exists t_e} = \{ x \in G / \delta_G(x, q) = \delta_G(e, q) \} = G_{\delta_G}$.

Note 3.11: Let δ_G be a CQFSI – group over U and $\{ t_0, t_1, t_2, t_3, \dots, t_n \} \in \text{Im}(\delta_G)$ which satisfying that $t_0 \geq t_1 \geq t_2 \geq t_3 \geq \dots \geq t_n$. Then the family of Upper – t – subgroups from a chain, which denoted by $C(\delta_G) = \delta_G^{\exists t_0} \supset \delta_G^{\exists t_1} \supset \dots \supset \delta_G^{\exists t_n}$. Not to our surprise, only some of the upper t – subgroups of δ_G form a chain. Since all the subgroups of G, In general, does not form a chain that is, it makes no sense to hope all the upper t – subgroups form a chain. In the connection, see example 1 $\{ 0, 3 \} \not\subset \{ 0, 2, 4 \}$ and $\{ 0, 2, 4 \} \not\subset \{ 0, 3 \}$. Of course if the number of the Im (δ_G) forms a chain, so does the upper t – subgroups of δ_G . For further detail, refer to the following theorem.

Theorem 3.12: Let G be a finite group, δ_G be a CQFSI – group over U and I be an arbitrary finite index set and $G(\delta_G^{\exists t}) = \{ \delta_G^{\exists t_i} / i \in I, t_i \in \text{Im}(\delta_G) \}$ then we have the followings:

- (i) There exists a unique $i_e \in I$ such that $t_{i_e} \geq t_i$, for all i.
- (ii) $G_{\delta_G} = \bigcap_{i \in I} \delta_G^{\exists t_i} = \delta_G^{\exists t_{i_e}}$
- (iii) $G = \bigcup_{i \in I} \delta_G^{\exists t_i}$
- (iv) If the members of Im (δ_G) forms a chain, so do is $G(\delta_G^{\exists t_i})$

Proof:

- (i) Since $\delta_G(e, q) \in \text{Im}(\delta_G)$, there exists a unique $i_e \in I$ such that $\delta_G(e, q) = t_{i_e}$. We know that $\delta_G(e, q) \geq \delta_G(x, q)$ for all $x \in G$ and $q \in Q$. It follows that $t_{i_e} \geq \delta_G(x, q)$, for all $x \in G$ and $q \in Q$. Thus $t_{i_e} \geq t_i$, for all $i \in I$.
- (ii) Since in theorem 3.11, it is proved that

$$G \delta_G = \delta_G^{\exists t_{ie}}, \text{ where } \delta_{G(e,q)} = t_{ie}.$$

It is only shows that $G \delta_G^{\exists t_{ie}} = \bigcap_{i \in I} \delta_G^{\exists t_i}$. Since $t_{ie} \geq t_i$ for all $i \in I$

$$G \delta_G^{\exists t_{ie}} \leq G \delta_G^{\exists t_i}, \text{ for all } i. \text{ Thus } G \delta_G^{\exists t_{ie}} \subseteq \bigcap_{i \in I} \delta_G^{\exists t_i}. \text{ Now let } x \in \bigcap_{i \in I} \delta_G^{\exists t_i}, \text{ then } x \in \delta_G^{\exists t_{ie}}, \text{ for}$$

all $i \in I$. This completes the proof.

Conclusion:

We construct a soft intersection group under certain conditions and a soft union group is investigated by this upper t-subgroups and lower t-subgroups with suitable examples. One can obtain the similar idea in the field of rough set theory and vague set theory.

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